

Perceptions of knowledge management in Brazilian software development companies

Professional information

1. 01 - Name

2. 02 - Email

3. 03 - Gender *

Female

Male

Prefer not to say

4. 04 - How old are you? (Only numbers) *

5. 05 - What is your current position? *

6. 06 - How many years of professional experience do you have in the area? (only numbers) *

7. 07 - What is your knowledge level in Knowledge Management?

- None
- Basic
- Intermediary
- Advanced

Company information

8. 01 - Company name

9. 02 - Company size *

- More than 1000 employees
- Between 51 and 100 employees
- Between 10 and 50 employees
- Less than 100 employees

10. 03 - Main segment (products developed) *

11. 04 - Company location (City/State) *

12. 05 - What software development methodologies does the company adopt? *

- Waterfall Model
- Incremental Model
- Spiral Model
- V-Modell XT
- Rational Unified Process (RUP)
- Scrum
- Extreme Programming (XP)
- None
- Others: _____

Knowledge Capture in the Company

13. CC.1 - Which of the following techniques do you use to capture knowledge in the company? *

- Interview experts
- Hear learning stories from other team members
- Apply questionnaires
- Observe the work of other team members
- Conduct simulations
- Participate in short and informal meetings (eg Brainstorming)
- Participate in formal meetings
- Training programs
- Others: _____

14. CC.2 - Once knowledge is captured or created, what are the most used ways to represent this knowledge in the company (codifying knowledge)? *

- Concept map
- Ontologies
- Flowchart
- Taxonomies
- Worksheets
- Manuals
- Report
- Requirements Documentation (Functional and Non-Functional Requirements)
- Unified Modeling Language (UML)
- Source code/comments
- Test cases
- User stories
- Others: _____

15. CC.3 - In your opinion, what are the company's main challenges in terms of capturing knowledge? *

Knowledge Sharing in the Company

16. DC.1 - What resources do you use to share knowledge in the company? *

- Formal meetings
- Short and informal meetings (eg Brainstorming)
- Formally written instructions
- Training program
- Wiki
- Discussion forum
- Blog
- Knowledge base
- Intranet
- Storytelling
- Knowledge Cafes
- Videos
- Mentoring
- Community of Practice (CoP)
- Others: _____

17. DC.2 - What knowledge type does the company usually share? *

- Lessons Learned
- Experiences
- Problem-solving
- Best practices
- Success histories
- Comments
- Others: _____

18. DC.3 - Which communication channel do you consider most useful for sharing knowledge? *

- Person communication
- Virtual meetings (e.g., email, forum, wiki, social networks)
- Other: _____

19. DC.4 - Considering the previous question (DC.3), why do you consider this channel more useful? *

20. DC.5 - Indicate how often knowledge sharing occurs in the company. *

	1	2	3	4	5	
Never	<input type="radio"/>	Always				

21. DC.6 - Indicate how well you think people know each other's knowledge and skills in the company *

	1	2	3	4	5	
Never	<input type="radio"/>	Always				

22. DC.7 -Indicate the frequency with which employees are motivated to share knowledge with each other in the company *

1 2 3 4 5

Never Always

23. DC.8 - Indicate how much you believe it is possible to trust the credibility of shared knowledge in the organization. *

1 2 3 4 5

Never Always

24. DC.9 - Indicate how often you share your knowledge with other team members in the company. *

1 2 3 4 5

Never Always

25. DC.10 - In your opinion, what are the main obstacles to sharing knowledge in the organization (when it occurs)? *

Knowledge Application in the Company

26. AC.1 - When you need to solve a work problem in the company, where do you usually seek knowledge? *

- Intranet
- Internet
- Knowledge base
- Manuals
- External professionals
- Source code
- Training program
- Others: _____

27. AC.3 - Your learning in the organization is easier when you use: *

- Tacit knowledge
- Explicit knowledge

28. AC.4 - What kind of tacitly presented information do you usually reuse in the company? *

- Ideas
- Advices
- Histories experiences past
- Skills of a colleague
- I do not reuse
- Others: _____

29. AC.5 - What kind of explicitly presented information/artifacts do you usually reuse in the company? *

- System
- Components (subsystems, modules)
- Functions (methods, classes)
- Libraries
- Test Script
- UML
- Database Scripts
- I do not reuse
- Others: _____

30. AC.6 - Do you know or use any knowledge management system? If yes, which one? *

31. AC.7 - In your opinion, what are the company's main challenges regarding the use of knowledge? *
